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TECHNOLOGY FOR SMART CITIES: THE PILLARS OF URBAN PLANNING OF THE FUTURE

(U.R.Oktyabirov, Tashkent university of architecture and civil engineering, independent researcher, uaktyabirov@gmail.com,

Annotation: The technical definition of a smart city - an urban area in which technology and sensors are used to collect data for resource management - may not sound all that exciting to the average citizen. While the “nuts and bolts” technology behind smart cities, such as artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things, is becoming better understood, what many people may not realize is just how big an impact combined smart city technology could have on the ways we live and work in the coming years.

Key words: smart-cities, big data, artificial intelligence, internet of things in cities, smart lighting

One of the most defining features of a smart city is its capacity to assimilate new technologies. However, what do we understand by technology for smart cities? No, it is not a list of devices “that make urban life easier”.

Self-driving cars, Big Data, robots, self-supply, remote public services... reveal the degree of urban intelligence on the surface. However, their integration is based on a more complex equation.

To resolve it, it is important to note that these smart city solutions are closely interrelated and generate effects at many levels. Precisely, the value of the technological revolution we are living is that the introduction of technology brings with it consequences at other levels. Therefore, many experts use the organic description and imagine a smart city as a living entity.

Smart technology applied to that organism enables it to scale evolutionary positions, as if it were 2001: A Space Odyssey. That is, the aim is not only to improve the quality of life of its inhabitants, but also to predict and tackle future challenges, which could even cast serious doubts on survival.³⁵

For example, in 2050, two thirds of the world’s population will live in a city. This simple statistic puts at risk the vital signs of any urban space in very basic terms of refuge, supply or sustainability. Turning to

technological intelligence means exploring an unprecedented route to combat these challenges (1 photo).

1 photo: Main challenges of planning smart cities

Big Data- Knowledge and information are great powers.³⁶ The key principle of empiricism in philosophy is transferred to our era in the development of Big Data. Now, the power not only consists of knowing, but in the mass management of that knowledge and its uses.

³⁵

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2022/07/27/smart-city-technologies-that-could-soon-change-the-way-we-live-and-work/?sh=34a0d7661be0>

³⁶ <https://nextrendsasia.org/5-learning-points-about-the-use-of-big-data-in-urban-design-and-planning/>

That is why Big Data is understood to be the new oil. The use of vast masses of data is key for public administrations and private corporations in terms, for example, of processing millions of files or controlling flows of transport.

Big Data should be aimed at strengthening the democratic values, security or social inclusion of cities. The luck of an oracle or “psychohistory” that aspires to solve current problems or before future ones make an appearance.

Artificial intelligence- Of course, humans are going to need a “little” help in managing this traffic of information and this help is coming from the development of artificial intelligence. The race for machines to integrate human processes is in full flow. It goes without saying that in the coming years we will have to deal with ethical conflicts that will emerge from their participation as is the case with the application of facial recognition algorithms. This technology can help increase security and reduce crime, while it also contradicts fundamental values such as privacy and non-discrimination.³⁷

The most visible aspect of this fourth industrial revolution, which is automation, can be found in robots. If a giant like Amazon had a thousand of them in 2013, they currently have more than 100,000. Future decades will undoubtedly be robotic.

As with Big Data, the real potential of artificial intelligence is not with what it can do for us, but rather the genuine solutions that it will provide us with thanks to machine learning.³⁸

Internet of things in cities- IoT is one of the most palpable and organic advances of a smart city. The integration of sensors and objects on the cloud have opened up a world of possibilities in all urban departments, from controlling energy flows, traffic or any incident in real time.

The aim of IoT is to boost the digitalization and interoperability of services provided by a city. That is the aim of the Vicinity project. This explains other applications and devices that have emerged thanks to connectivity and which form part of the DNA of this revolution for life and even death, in cities.

Connectivity- If we talk about connectivity, we cannot ignore, in terms of infrastructure, another technological pillar of cities: smart communication networks. Today this is strongly related to the implementation of 5G, but it is not the only area in which telecommunications work.

5G will contribute to the improvement of IoT by allowing the interconnection of up to 20 billion devices. It will also help in terms of energy sustainability.

Toward a model of sustainability- The reduction of energy bills by exploring new forms of producing and managing existing models is essential in order to talk of the future (or of life on the Earth’s crust). This is another structural factor that is integrated in the genetics of technologies for smart cities.

We can find it in the exploitation of renewable energies or in waste management. In this war against pollution, we may still have a few battles to lose.

2 photo: IT solutions for smart cities

Smart lighting- The solutions seen until now provide a new structural perspective. However, there are other related developments that foster sustainable alternatives. Such is the case of smart lighting systems. Cities such as Copenhagen have achieved energy savings of up

³⁷ <https://www.aiplusinfo.com/blog/artificial-intelligence-and-urban-design/>

³⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264275120313408>

to 65%. Likewise, they are also a ray of hope for the growing problem of light pollution.

Transport networks in a smart city-Transport will be one of the areas that will see the most developments. Electrification and self-driving vehicles are directing the automotive industry today. The former entails the improvement of batteries; the latter, the enormous challenge of applying artificial intelligence to mobility.

Every smart city dream of improving the quality of life of its inhabitants. If we dissect this concept, the creation of sustainable and inclusive environments are particularly relevant among the benefits we have mentioned.

In fact, inclusion is a paradigm for smart cities. They cannot allow themselves the luxury of ignoring it. Almost all smart technologies convey a moral perspective aimed at advancing fairness and equity. These can do a great deal, for example, for disabled persons.

It is clear that, in the new urban era opening up before us, the most human side of technology

is yet to be explored. Just as the hive concept is inseparable from the bee concept, a technologically “inhuman” city cannot aspire to be anything other than a failed oxymoron.

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117.	<i>Маноев Бахрон,</i> - РОЛЬ И КОМПОЗИЦИЯ ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫХ ЗДАНИЙ В ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ	484-486
118.	<i>Тўйчиева Нозима Тоир қизи</i> - ДУНЁНИНГ ТУРЛИ МАМЛАКАТЛАРИДАГИ ҚИШЛОҚ УЙЛАРИ ХАМДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ХУДУДИДАГИ ҚИШЛОҚ УЙЛАРИ. ТУРИЗМ ҚИШЛОҚЛАРИ.	487-490
119.	<i>Б.Т. Абдурахмонов,</i> ДАМ ОЛИШ МАСКАНЛАРИНИНГ ЛОЙИХАЛАШГА ТАЪСИР ЭТУВЧИ ОМИЛЛАРИ.	491-493
120.	<i>Мелиева Чиннигул Отакуловна, Тугалов Аброрбек Дилмурод угли-</i> СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА	494-496
121.	<i>I.M.Qosimov.</i> ЖАМОАТ BINOLARINI ARXITEKTURAVIY RIVOJLANTIRISH (KASBGA YO‘NALTIRISH MARKAZLARI MISOLIDA)	497-499
122.	<i>Yaхуayev A.A., Usmonov Samariddin Samat o‘g‘li</i> - TOSHKENT SHAHRIDAGI OLIY TA‘LIM MUASASALARI HAMDA TALABALAR-TURAR JOYLARINING TAHLILI	500-502
123.	<i>Rasulova F.S.,Ashirov G‘.</i> - CHIZMACHILIK FANGA OID TUSHUNCHALARNI TALABALARGA O‘QITISHNING ZARURIYATI	503-505
124.	<i>Babakulova Mukaddas Norkabulovna. Radjabova Ruxshona Raimovna,</i> - ТА‘ЛИМ ЖАРAYONIDA TALABALARNING SAMARALI BILISH BOSQICHLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHGA INNOVATSION YONDASHUV	506-509
125.	<i>A.T.Xotamov, C.Y. Рашидов</i> - КЎП КВАРТИРАЛИ УЙЛАРНИ ТЕХНИК ХОЛАТИНИ МОНИТОРИНГ ҚИЛИШДА ЭЛЕКТРОН ПАСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ АФЗАЛЛИКЛАРИ.	510-513
126.	<i>Тўйчиева Нозима Тоир қизи</i> - ЯНГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН – ИЖТИМОИЙ СИЁСИЙ ДАВЛАТ.	514-517
127.	<i>Davlatov Ikrom Shavxidinovich</i> - ШАНАР СИYOSATINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHI.	518-520
	5-SHO‘BA. "RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA BARQAROR SHAHARSOZLIK RIVOJLANISHINI TA‘MINLASH. TASHKILIY TIZIMLAR VA TECHNOLOGIK JARAYONLARDA AXBOROT TECHNOLOGIYALARI VA MODELLASHTIRISH"	
128.	<i>Ганчерёнок Игорь Иванович, Горбачёв Николай Николаевич, Рахимов Абдуазиз Рахмонович,</i> - СТРАНОВАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ	521-524
129.	<i>Маноев Саид Бахронович,</i> ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ АНАЛИЗЕ И ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИИ ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬНЫХ КОМПЛЕКСОВ ЗДАНИЙ	525-528
130.	<i>U.R.Oktyabirov,</i> TECHNOLOGY FOR SMART CITIES: THE PILLARS OF URBAN PLANNING OF THE FUTURE	529-531
131.	<i>Safarov Raxmon ,Xudoyberdiyev Sardor Ismoilovich,</i> SUV TA‘MINOTI TARMOQLARINING UZLUKSIZ ISHLASH EHTIMOLLARINI BAHOLASHNING MATEMATIK MODELI	532-534
132.	<i>U.R.Oktyabirov,</i> DIGITAL URBAN PLANNING	535-537
133.	<i>Xakimxon Hamzayevich Xikmatov, Nilufar Ergashevna Sulaymanova,</i> DAVOLASH JARAYONINI STATISTIK TAHLILIDA IQTISODIY-MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISH USULLARNI QO‘LLASH	538-541